

On the Stability of Nickel Ferrocyanide Sol in Ultrasonic Field: Sono Dispersion of Nickel Ferrocyanide

Satya Prakash, Om Prakash and Sheo Prakash

Negatively charged, dirty green coloured nickel ferrocyanide sol has been prepared by subjecting the precipitate of nickel ferrocyanide in double-distilled water to ultrasonic radiation. The amount of dispersion increases with the increase in time of exposure. The sol thus prepared becomes more stable on ultrasonication. pH , specific conductivity increase while the optical density decreases as the exposure time is prolonged. The enhanced stability is attributed to the hydrolysis of the sol. Also, the cavitation which further breaks down the bigger particles into finer ones is responsible for the greater stability of the sol. Presence of oxygen is not essential for the ultrasonic stabilization of the sol. Hydrogen peroxide has practically no effect on the stability of the sol.

The coagulating and the stabilizing effects of high frequency inaudible sound waves on various colloidal systems have been studied by a number of investigators. Prakash and coworkers¹⁻³ in their previous communications have published their results on such colloidal systems as ceric hydroxide, vanadium pentoxide, silver, selenium and tellurium hydrosols. The study of sono-chemical reactions and the sono-dispersion in absence of oxygen has drawn considerable attention in recent years. Depending on their results some workers⁴⁻⁷ viewed that the presence of oxygen is essential to bring about chemical reactions while others⁸⁻¹⁰ completely ruled out such condition. But so far as colloidal systems are concerned, no such attempts to study the influence of ultrasonics on them in absence of oxygen have been made. In one of the publications¹¹ from this laboratory it has been reported that the ultrasonic coagulation of manganese dioxide sol is inhibited when the oxygen was eliminated by nitrogen. In this paper we are communicating our results on the study of the stability of nickel ferrocyanide under ultrasonic radiation where the sol itself was prepared ultrasonically.

EXPERIMENTAL

The source of ultrasonic power was a high frequency ultrasonic generator of Mullard

1. Prakash and Ghosh, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1959, 14, 338.
2. *Ibid*, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1958, 168, 33.
3. Prakash and Pandey, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1959, 167, 39; 1963, 190, 60 and 135.
4. Virtanen and Ellfolk, *Acta Chem. Scand.* 1950, 4, 93.
5. Lindstrom, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 1955, 27, 654.
6. Kling and Kling, *Compt. rend.*, 1946, 229, 33.
7. Wawrzyniec, Bardzicki, and Brozek, *Proc. Polish Conf. Ultrasonics* 2nd 1956 (Published 1957) 95-B.
8. Schmid, *Naturwiss.*, 1950, 37, 16.
9. Weisler, *J. Acoust. Soc., Am.*, 1953, 25, 651.
10. Prudhomme, *Bull. Soc., Chim. Biol.*, 1957, 39, 425.
11. Prakash and Prakash, *Kolloid Z.* 1963, 188, 136.

type E-7562. The electrical input to the barium titanate transducer with a frequency of 1 Mc/Sec was 225 watts per sq. cm. The crystal was kept in bath of water maintained at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$ and the distance between the vessel and crystal was so adjusted as to get the maximum fountain. The arrangement of ultrasonic bath has already been illustrated elsewhere².

Decinormal solutions of nickel chloride and potassium ferrocyanide were mixed together, the latter being in excess. The precipitate of nickel ferrocyanide was filtered and washed. The precipitate was put into double distilled water in a Jena glass bottle and was exposed to ultrasonic waves. The nickel ferrocyanide sol of dirty green colour was obtained within half an hour. In this way sufficient amount of the sol was prepared and stored in a Jena bottle for detailed studies. The sol was purified by dialysis for three days. The concentration of the sols was determined by evaporating a known volume of the sol to dryness on the water bath. The sol concentration was found to be 8.762 g/l.

Above sol, 30 ml., were taken in a 250 ml flat bottomed ground glass stoppered Jena glass vessel and exposed to the action of ultrasonic waves for different intervals of time. The stability of the sol was determined after each exposure by noting the amount of potassium chloride and barium chloride required to coagulate the negatively charged sol of nickel ferrocyanide in a fixed time (30 minutes) and the results are given in Tables I and II. The variation in hydrogen ion concentration and specific conductivity of the sol shown in figures 2 and 3 was also recorded. Transmission in percentage was determined with a Unicam SP-1400 prism absorptiometer and the optical density was calculated by the equation, Optical density = $\log (1/T)$, where T is transmission.

The experiments were also carried out in the absence of oxygen. The air of the bottle containing the sol was replaced with nitrogen by bubbling for half an hour. Nitrogen from gas cylinder was previously passed through solutions of vanadous sulphate and alkaline pyrogallol to remove oxygen. The sol was studied at two dilutions A and A/2 where A is the concentration of the original sol.

TABLE I

Volume of sol A = 2 ml., Total volume = 8 ml.
Time allowed for coagulation, 30 mts., Temp. = $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$, R.F. output voltage = 2.4 KV.

Time of exposure in minutes	In presence of air		In absence of oxygen	
	M/10 KCl	Coagulation values in ml. with M/100 BaCl ₂		M/100 BaCl ₂
0	4.90	1.50	4.90	1.50
60	5.50	1.90	5.45	1.85
120	5.90	2.00	5.80	2.00
180	6.05	2.10	6.00	2.10
240	6.20	2.20	6.20	2.20

TABLE II

Sol A/2

Time of exposure in minutes	In presence of air		In absence of oxygen	
	M/10 KCl	Coagulation values M/100 BaCl ₂	Coagulation values in ml. with M/10 KCl	M/100 BaCl ₂
0	3.90	1.00	3.90	1.00
60	4.30	1.25	4.25	1.20
120	4.55	1.30	4.50	1.30
180	4.75	1.40	4.70	1.35
240	4.80	1.50	4.75	1.50

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is evident from Fig. 1 that the amount of dispersion of nickel ferrocyanide increases rapidly with the time of exposure in the beginning but after some times the rate of dispersion becomes slow and it seems to have attained an optimum value. The sol on ultra-

FIG. 1. ULTRASONIC DISPERSION OF NICKEL-FERROCYANIDE

sonoration becomes more stable in both the cases, i.e., in presence as well as in absence of oxygen. Tables I and II reveal that the sol requires an increasing amount of potassium chloride and barium chloride, as the irradiation time is enhanced to coagulate the sol in fixed time. The experiments performed in nitrogen atmosphere eliminating oxygen and in presence of air do not show any observable difference in ultrasonic stabilization.

The nickel ferrocyanide sol is negatively charged and its stability is mainly due to the adsorption of ferrocyanide and hydroxyl ions. Dhar and collaborators¹² have shown

that ferrocyanide sols are appreciably hydrolysed in aqueous solution and this hydrolysis makes the sol more stable. It might be possible that due to mechanical action and cavitation energy nickel ferrocyanide sol gets more hydrolysed. Ferrocyanic acid being a weak acid, the salt of it when hydrolyses, there is an increase in the hydroxyl ion concentration and this goes to increase the alkalinity of the sol. The explanation is substantiated by our results that pH of the sol goes on increasing as the time of exposure is increased (Fig. 2). Some of these hydroxyl ions are absorbed in the colloidal phase and consequently

FIG. 2. VARIATION IN pH WITH TIME OF EXPOSURE

the sol is further stabilised. The observed increase in specific conductivity of the sol (Fig. 3) is predominantly due to the release of hydroxyl ions. Whenever water or an aqueous solution is exposed to ultrasonic waves hydrogen peroxide is produced¹³ and in presence of air

FIG. 3. VARIATION IN SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY WITH TIME OF EXPOSURE

13. Polotskii, *J. Gen. Chem. (USSR)*, 1947, 17, 649.

nitrous and nitric acid are also formed¹⁴ in traces. These substances do also contribute towards the conductivity and pH, but only to a very small extent in view of their very small concentrations. Simultaneously, there is a marked hydrolysis of nickel ferrocyanide which affects pH as well as the conductivity. This being more pronounced, we find that in our case, pH and conductivity are both increased.

The nature of the variation of optical density with time is identical for the unexposed and exposed sols. In both cases the absorption maximum occurs at 610 m μ , suggesting that no change in the basic character of the substance has taken place. It seems that the ultrasonic waves have brought about a change in physical character of the particles by its cavitating actions on larger aggregates making them further small. This also accounts for the greater stability of the sol in ultrasonic field.

The effect of ultrasonics on this sol cannot be accounted for on the basis of the formation of hydrogen peroxide in the system, since practically no change in stability of the sol takes place on the addition of hydrogen peroxide in the system from outside. This fact is further ascertained by the results that there is hardly any observable difference in the effect of ultrasonic waves on this sol in presence as well as in absence of oxygen. The formation of hydrogen peroxide in water, on sonolysis, is considerably reduced in absence of oxygen, therefore, if hydrogen peroxide had any major contribution towards the stability of the sol in ultrasonic field, the effect of ultrasonics on this sol in absence of oxygen should have been reduced. In other words the role of oxygen in relation to the activity of ultrasonic waves towards this sol is not very significant. Its presence merely provides permanent gas nuclei for the onset of cavitation. This, however, does not play any role in initiating the secondary oxidation reactions which may affect the stability of the sol as has been observed in cases of chromium hydroxide and selenium hydrosols.

The authors are indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, India, for providing financial assistance to one of the authors (Dr. Om Prakash).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD (INDIA).

Received, July 1, 1965.

14. Akiya and Okui, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1947, 67, 232.